

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY

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28th March, 1972

Dear Andrew,

Over the weekend I was able to button-hole David Peacock to ask if he could arrange for a few of the sand-tempered Sassanian sherds from Siraf, Oman, and Yahya/Dasht-i-Deh to be analysed. I thought that this might at least show whether they had^a common origin, possibly in the Minab area. I failed to get David Whitehouse on the phone today to ask if he would provide a couple of sherds and wondered if he had already gone abroad. If so, do you know who is working on his Sassanian levels and if it would be possible to procure two specimen sherds? Could you also part with a couple, if possible from both Yahya and Dasht-i-Deh. I'd be most grateful for your help.

Yours,

J. B. Trice

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Oxford.